

RDA Governance Document

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Authors: Research Data Alliance

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Abstract: The role of the RDA Governance Document is to describe the structures of the RDA, and their relationships, that support the activity and principles of the RDA, and Council's powers and authority. The Governance Document is the responsibility of the RDA Council.

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RDA Governance Document

Researchers and innovators openly share and reuse data across technologies, disciplines, and countries to address the grand challenges of society

The current global research data landscape is highly fragmented, by disciplines or by domains, from oceanography, life sciences and health, to agriculture, space and climate. When it comes to cross-disciplinary activities, the notions of "building blocks" of common data infrastructures and building specific "data bridges" are becoming accepted metaphors for approaching the data complexity and enable data sharing and reuse. The Research Data Alliance enables data to be shared and reused across barriers through outputs developed by focused Working Groups and Interest Groups, formed of experts from around the world and drawn from academia, industry and government. Participation in the RDA is open to anyone who agrees to its guiding principles of openness, consensus, balance, harmonisation, with a community driven and non-profit and technology-neutral approach.

The role of this RDA Governance Document is to describe the guiding principles of the RDA, its structures and their relationships, and Council's powers, authority and responsibilities. The Governance Document is the responsibility of the RDA Council.

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LOG

V.1	Initial published version (originally working draft 3)
V.2	Updated to reflect the work of the OAB Task Force to clarify the roles of the OAB and Organizational Assembly and maintenance of the Organisation Plan
V.3	Revised figure 2. Expanded introduction. Comments from a law firm helping establish the RDA Charity.
V.4 + changes	Base version: V4, dated Oct 2013 + draft changes by Stefanie Kethers in April 2015, in consultation with Mark Parsons
V.5	Changes by RW
V.5.1	Comments from AT, further changes by RW and SK
V5.2	As approved by Council in June 2015
Revisions 2018 V1	Revisions 2018: to revise the RDA Governance Document in line with the new 2018 RDA Strategy
2018 V1.1	Version that went to Council on 14 Feb 2018, following input from Council subgroup and TAB and OAB Chairs
2018 V1.9	Consistency check by AT following on from contributions from KA, AN, JB, BM and others
2018 V2	Final tidy up post Council meeting in Berlin
2018 V2.1	Reorder of headings and consistency check
2018 V2.2	Minor edits, conversion of future tense to present tense (where this makes sense)
2018 V2.3	Version approved by Council on 9 July 2018
2019 V2.4	Version being worked on by Mark Leggott, Bridget Walker, Stefanie Kethers in December 2019
2020 V2.5	Final edits made after review by Mark Leggott, Bridget Walker, Stefanie Kethers and Council. Added Regional Members and RAB.
2020 V2.6	Final edits made to align with OAB, TAB and Regional Processes documents
2020 V2.7	Final revision based on a review by Council.
2020 V2.8	Final version including revisions by Secretary General, including Communities of Practice
2021 V2.9	Inclusion of Legal Entity headquarters host organization, update to Council and Financial Subcommittee membership
2023 V3.0	Update to Council Election process from 2023
2025 V3.1	Update to References, URLs and DOIs as a result of web migration in 2024

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Introduction and Guiding Principles

The goal of the Research Data Alliance is to accelerate international data-driven innovation and discovery by facilitating research data sharing and exchange. This is achieved through the development, adoption, and deployment of infrastructure, policy, practice, standards, and other outputs, as expressed in the RDA Mission: “The Research Data Alliance (RDA) builds the social and technical bridges that enable open sharing and reuse of data”.

To effectively facilitate the achievement of this goal, members of the RDA are asked to subscribe to the following Guiding Principles that underlie and steer the conduct and evolution of the organization.

Guiding Principles of the RDA:

- **Openness** - Individual membership is open to all interested individuals who subscribe to the RDA's Guiding Principles. The RDA community meetings and processes are open, and the outputs of RDA Working Groups are publicly disseminated;
- **Consensus** - The RDA moves forward by achieving consensus among its membership. The RDA processes and procedures include appropriate mechanisms to resolve conflicts;
- **Inclusive** - The RDA seeks to promote broad, balanced and inclusive representation of its membership and stakeholder communities;
- **Harmonization** - The RDA works to achieve harmonization across data standards, policies, technologies, infrastructure, and communities;
- **Community-driven** - The RDA is a public, community-driven body constituted of volunteer members and organisations, supported by the RDA Secretariat;
- **Non-profit and technology-neutral** - the RDA does not promote, endorse, or sell commercial products, technologies, or services and the development of open and re-usable recommendations and outputs within the RDA is mandatory.

Individual members are also required to abide by the [RDA Code of Conduct](#)¹.

Individual RDA membership is free and open to all interested individuals who subscribe to the RDA's Guiding Principles. Organisations can also become members of the RDA; this is not free but does bring additional advantages. More information on individual and organisational membership can be found in the next sections.

Participation and Involvement

Individual Member Participation

Individual Members are actively involved in the work of the RDA and can participate through:

- Working Groups, which are engaged in creating outputs that will directly enable data sharing, exchange, or interoperability. Working Groups operate to achieve a defined objective on a finite timeline. These are described in their endorsed Statement of Works and agreed upon establishment. Upon completion of the Working Group effort (typically 18 months) as described within the endorsed Statement of Work, a Working Group has a number of options for continuing or disbanding². Working Group membership is open to all RDA members; members are volunteers who may be supported by their sponsors or be self-motivated.

¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/code-of-conduct/>

² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/closing-rda-groups/>

- Interest Groups³, which are composed of experts from the community that are committed to directly or indirectly enabling data sharing, exchange, or interoperability. Interest Groups serve as a platform for communication and coordination among individuals, outside and within the RDA, with shared interests. They produce important deliverables such as surveys, recommendations, reports, and Working Group Statements of Work (SoW). Interest Group membership is open to all RDA members; members are volunteers who may be supported by their sponsors or be self-motivated. Interest Groups can continue meeting until they become inactive.
- Communities of Practice⁴ form to build discipline or domain specific communities within RDA as well as to investigate, discuss and provide knowledge and skills on any specific discipline and/or research domain issues relevant to the community and RDA. CoPs are composed of experts from that community that have an interest in the discipline / research domain and are committed to directly or indirectly enabling data sharing, exchange, and/or interoperability. CoPs serve as platforms for communication and coordination among individuals, building bridges outside and within the RDA, with shared interests.
- The Plenary⁵, which is the bi-annual meeting of the RDA. Attendance at the Plenary is strongly encouraged and open to all RDA Members.
- Discussions within the scope of the RDA. Any RDA member may participate in the use of the official RDA online platform⁶.

Organisational Member Participation

Organisations may join the RDA. Organisational Members (OMs) provide organisational and operational guidance to Council and the Secretary General. They support the RDA by encouraging and facilitating the adoption of relevant RDA outputs among organisational members to drive broad adoption. OMs should share some or all of the RDA goals and work according to its guiding principles. OMs can be of any type, and currently include R&D agencies, for-profit companies and non-profit foundations, community organisations and research institutions. OMs must make an application for membership and are required to pay member fees according to the schedule set out by the RDA⁷.

It is desirable that OMs of the RDA

- work to accelerate international data-driven innovation and discovery by facilitating research data sharing and exchange, use and re-use, standards harmonisation, and discoverability; and
- nominate and send an RDA Individual Member as representative to attend and vote in the Organisational Assembly (OA) meetings.

The OMs of the RDA also receive the right to put forward candidates for the Organisational Advisory Board, one of the RDA's key governing bodies. Amongst other roles, the Assembly is invited to comment on RDA Working Group proposals before acceptance and to review the outputs of Working and Interest Groups from an adoption perspective.

The Organisational Assembly (OA) is the body of representatives from the OMs and Affiliates (see below). The OA meets during RDA Plenaries. The OA also elects the Organisational Advisory Board (OAB), which provides advice to the Council on adoption of RDA Outputs, and the directions, processes, and mechanisms of the RDA. At least one chair of the OAB serves as a non-voting consensus-forming member of Council.

The processes governing Organisational Members, Organisational Affiliates, the Organisational Assembly and the Organisational Advisory Board are described in the [Organisational Membership](#)

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/create-an-interest-group/>

⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/communities-of-practice/>

⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/>

⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/organisational-membership/>

[Processes](#) document⁸.

Affiliation with Other Organisations

The Research Data Alliance works with like-minded organisations to coordinate efforts in mutual areas of interest and to avoid unnecessary duplication and conflict. Each Organisational Affiliation will be considered on its own merit, and the circumstances will determine the approach to collaboration in each case. There are no financial considerations on either side, but there should be demonstrable mutual benefit from the affiliation. For example, Affiliates are expected to participate actively in RDA activities and to present a summary of their relevant organisational activities to RDA. They will be invited to attend the Organisational Members session(s), to vote in Organisational Advisory Board elections, and can run for and be elected to the Organisational Advisory Board. Affiliates will in turn reciprocate the affiliation status to RDA where appropriate.

An exchange of Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) letters will formalise the relationship, which can be terminated on request by either party.

The criteria for organisations to become Affiliate members are the following:

- Have a related mission to RDA and directly or indirectly contribute to data sharing and interoperability
- Work globally
- Define and implement explicit points of collaboration with RDA in an MoU such as joint WG/IG/CoP, adoption agreements, shared services, etc. which would deliver mutual benefits
- Provide an equivalent affiliate role for RDA in their organisation (preferably with voting rights)

The processes governing Organisational Affiliates are described in the Organisational Membership Processes document⁷.

Regional Participation

An RDA Region is loosely defined as a national level geographic entity or consortium of national-level entities and is intended to be broadly representative. The RDA will not decide the level at which Regions should be formed. It is for the individual countries or consortia to define what model best suits their context and culture. This decision should remain flexible and open to change as circumstances require. Other groups that may convene around a non-geographic focus (e.g., Chemistry) should form Communities of Practice (CoP), Interest or Working Groups according to the work of the structure of the RDA.

The Regional Assembly (RA) is a body that consists of all interested, engaged, committed and partner RDA Regions and represents the interests of the Regions to the RDA. The Regional Assembly will help connect parallel programmes across Regions (e.g., adoption grants) and promote the creation/development of other regions.

The Regional Advisory Board (RAB) will be composed of elected members representing partner Regions from the Regional Assembly. Co-Chairs will be elected to participate in the Council as non-voting consensus-forming members to maximize the benefits of Regions to the RDA and the RDA to the Regions. Co-Chairs will bring issues and concerns from Regions to the Council, and from the Council to members.

Regions will contribute to the cost of RDA business operations through financial and in-kind support. The level of contribution that is appropriate for each region will be agreed bilaterally between the RDA and the Region.

⁸ Research Data Alliance. (2021). RDA Organisational Membership Processes (9 September 2020). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/2921FEB4-B68B-452D-AC5A-6B90B22E4C91>

The processes governing RDA Regions are described in the RDA Regional Processes Document⁹.

Governing and Supporting Bodies of the RDA

The governing and supporting bodies of the RDA provide the environment to support the work of the Individual Members, Organisational Members and Affiliates, Regional Members, Communities of Practice, Interest Groups, Working Groups, and Plenary, and ensure that the organisational perspective remains focused on the longer term aims of the Research Data Alliance.

The RDA Governing Bodies are:

- **Council:** The Council is responsible for maintaining the vision of the RDA, ensuring the guiding principles and Code of Conduct of the organisation are maintained, and formally endorsing official RDA documents, group Statements of Work (SoW), as well as the outcomes of RDA activities in line with RDA principles. The Council is responsible for the overall oversight, success, strategy, and sustainability of the RDA. The powers and authority of the Council are described in this document. Council members are the Trustees of the Research Data Alliance Foundation (legal entity) and have the financial and legal responsibilities described in the Articles of Association. Details of the processes governing Council membership and responsibilities are described in the Organisational and Process Plan document.
- **TAB:** The Technical Advisory Board (TAB) is responsible for the technical direction of the RDA and provides technical expertise and advice to the Council, as well as helping to develop and review RDA Working and Interest Groups and Communities of Practice to promote their impact and effectiveness. Membership of the TAB is elected from the RDA membership. At least one Co-Chair of the Technical Advisory Board serves as a non-voting consensus-forming member of the Council and of the OAB. The responsibilities of the Technical Advisory Board are described in the RDA TAB Responsibilities and Processes document.
- **OAB:** The Organisational Advisory Board (OAB) provides advice to the RDA Council. The OAB advises the Council on the adoption of outputs, directions, processes, and mechanisms of the RDA. At least one Co-Chair of the OAB serves as a non-voting consensus-forming member of the Council. The responsibilities of the OAB are described in the Organisational Membership Process document.
- **RAB:** The Regional Advisory Board (RAB) provides advice to the RDA Council on regional opportunities and issues. The RAB advises the Council on the adoption of outputs, directions, processes, and mechanisms of the RDA in the regions. At least one Co-Chair of the RAB serves as a non-voting consensus-forming member of the Council.

The RDA Supporting Body is:

- **Secretariat:** The Secretariat supports the administrative, logistical, and other activities of the RDA by implementing the processes defined in the planning documents. This includes supporting the Membership and Bodies of the RDA in their undertaking of RDA activities. The Secretariat is responsible for the documentation of how the RDA works, its decision-making mechanisms, and general processes. The Secretariat is led by a Secretary General who is appointed by and reports to the Council. The Secretary General serves as a non-voting consensus-forming member of the Council. The Secretariat is responsible for the operation of the RDA including development and maintenance of the annual work plan. An annual budget proposal is prepared by the Secretariat for Council review and approval.

An individual can only serve in a voting capacity on one of the RDA governing and supporting bodies at a time.

In addition to the above formal RDA bodies, the chairs of the Working and Interest Groups typically meet informally at Plenaries (when the TAB holds a joint session with them to discuss issues of common interest. These meetings are not official RDA meetings.

⁹ Research Data Alliance. (2021). RDA Regional Partnership Processes Document (2.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00059>

RDA Constituent Bodies in Detail

This section provides more detail for each of the constituent bodies (which include the governing and supporting bodies outlined above) of the RDA. All RDA constituent bodies, and their members are expected to uphold the RDA Guiding Principles and follow the RDA Code of Conduct.

The Structure

The Community of RDA

The Work of RDA

The Business of RDA

Figure 1 - Overview of Research Data Alliance Governance and Operational Support

Individual Members

Function	Active involvement in the work of the RDA.
Membership	Membership is open to any individual who subscribes to the RDA Guiding Principles and Code of Conduct.
Joining	Any individual may join the Research Data Alliance; they do so through the RDA website ¹⁰ .
Leaving	Members may leave by contacting the Secretariat for removal from the RDA mailing lists and databases. Individual Membership can be revoked in respect of any member who is found not to be operating in line with the aims of the RDA or adhering to its Code of Conduct ¹ .
Duration	There is no term limit on membership.
Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Members may participate in all RDA Plenaries, Communities of Practice, Working and Interest Groups and other open activities. Members receive regular updates on the work of the RDA.
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Members are expected to subscribe to the Guiding Principles of the RDA. Members are required to abide by the RDA Code of Conduct. Members are encouraged to be active members, i.e., to participate in RDA discussions, Interest Groups, Working Groups, Plenaries, etc.

¹⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/register/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Members are encouraged to comment on Candidate Statements of Work (SoW), RDA Outputs, plans and documents, and within open community discussions. • Members are encouraged to promote the RDA and its outputs to the broader community to contribute to the effectiveness and the impact of the organisation. • Members are encouraged to acknowledge and cite RDA¹¹ when referencing outputs, making presentations, in publications, etc.
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Organisational Members

Function	To provide an organisational perspective on the work of the RDA, to provide perspective on current and future technical requirements and to enhance adoption of the outputs of RDA Working Groups, Interest Groups and Communities of Practice. Organisational Members and Affiliates designate Individual Members as representatives to the Organisational Assembly.
Membership	Membership is open to any organisation that subscribes to the RDA Guiding Principles, the RDA Code of Conduct, completes a membership template and submits the required fees.
Joining	Organisational Members apply to join through the RDA website ⁷ .
Leaving	Organisational Membership is annual and is renewed upon payment of an annual fee. The Council approves and removes Organisational Affiliates and delegates the decision on Organisational Member expiration (e.g. non-payment of annual fee) and revocation (e.g. non-compliance with the RDA guiding principles and code of conduct) to the OAB. In the event of an appeal, the Council makes the final decision.
Duration	There is no term limit on membership.
Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attend Organisational Assembly meetings and elect the Organisational Advisory Board and its Co-Chairs • Receive regular updates on the work of the RDA, including updates directly from the RDA Council at each Plenary • Provide advice to the RDA Council through the Organisational Advisory Board • Be recognized on the RDA website and at RDA Plenary meetings as a supporter of data sharing, data interoperability and Open Science in general • Influence the RDA work and directions on research data management and Open Science in their sectors, markets and geographies
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate open job positions in the organisation to whole RDA community • Early-bird reduced RDA Plenary registration fee for all Organisational Members extended through to the start of the Plenary • Have the opportunity to act as early adopters of RDA Recommendations and other outputs • Exchange news, strategies and policies across regions

¹¹ For example, “This work was developed as part of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) Group entitled ‘long name (short name)’, and we acknowledge the support provided by the RDA community and structures” – see <https://www.rd-alliance.org/communication-kit/for more advice>

Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work towards the aims of the RDA and subscribe to the RDA Guiding Principles. • Contribute financial support to the RDA at a level defined in the published fee structure for the term of their membership. • Participate in the Organisational Assembly. • Generally, adhere to the Norms for Contributing to and Using RDA Products¹² when contributing to the development, review, and implementation of formal RDA Recommendations.
Further information	Further information about the OA and the OAB can be found in the Organisational Membership Processes document.

Regional Members

Function	To provide a Regional perspective on the work of the RDA ⁹ . Regions run activities to support growth in RDA membership and adoption of outputs in the local area. Experience of building communities, running events, promoting standards and having effective communication channels is a strength. Convening multi-stakeholder groups to administer and oversee regional activities is preferred.
Partnership	Any region that negotiates a Partnership agreement with the RDA can become an RDA Region.
Joining	Regions join RDA through a formal partnership agreement that is initiated through discussions with the RDA Secretary General. Acceptance by the RDA of Regional Partnership is contingent on an agreed contribution, which can be monetary, in-kind, or both.
Leaving	The relationship between RDA and an RDA Region can be terminated on request by either party.
Duration	There is no term limit on membership.
Rights	Ultimately, the RDA authorises and gives validity to the Regions. It is the RDA that provides the forum for the global community to connect and share knowledge that provides the context in which Regions operate. RDA supports the work of the Regions by various means.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disseminating Regional efforts to the global RDA community: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ promotion/communication of regional activities via RDA Global website, listservs, social media, newsletter and marketing materials; ○ putting Regions on the global map and amplifying their activities to international audiences. • Facilitating connections & shared interests among regions to support activities and growth by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ providing a forum for sharing knowledge across regions and co-locating events; ○ offering networking opportunities and supporting the sharing of expertise; ○ assisting in adoption programmes across regions. • Supporting Regional leadership to build the RDA community and create impact by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ assisting in lobbying for data issues within the Region.

¹² <https://archive.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-outputs-and-ip-task-force/wiki/norms-contributing-and-using-rda-products.html>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ leveraging Secretariat attendance at regional events to help advocate for RDA; ○ providing resources to help with advocacy and dissemination (e.g. sample slide decks, statistics and branding materials for reuse); ○ offering small grants (or collaborate on the application for funding) to assist with the creation/development of Regional activities. ● Rotating Plenary locations, enabling international consensus to be built on issues of Regional importance. ● Hosting Regional Assembly (RA) meetings. The views of RDA Regions are represented in the Council through the RAB Co-Chairs. ● Providing advice to the Council through the RAB. <p>The RDA also supports the Regions in their business activities in a variety of ways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Supporting Regional development, administration, and leadership by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ liaising with the Secretariat on information (e.g., membership data) that needs to be gathered to inform and support their activities ○ sharing monthly statistics on Regional membership and activity, as permitted by legal frameworks (e.g. GDPR), to enable engagement and growth; ○ compiling wider statistics and other contextual information from a global perspective; ○ featuring Regions and Regional activities in global RDA communications vehicles; ○ developing joint arrangements with Regions to create a more formal collaboration. ● Providing organisational support for Regionally-hosted RDA Plenaries with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Secretariat staff time; ○ Plenary registration administration support; ○ Plenary website hosting; ○ communication and marketing support. ● Establishing a Regional Assembly and Regional Advisory Board to ensure Regions have an appropriate function/role and influence as outlined in the relevant sections of this document.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inviting funders from contributing Regions to participate in the Funders Forum. ● Supporting Regional leadership to achieve fundraising goals. ● Assisting in making the case to Regional funders and providing advocacy. ● Providing inputs to proposals in which the RDA is being included as a partner. ● Providing sample Statement of Works, reusable text and statistics on RDA, impact stories. ● Hosting Regional websites. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To build the RDA community by profiling Regions, adoption cases and calls/scholarship programmes, Regions will be provided with their own, customisable websites within an overarching RDA multi-site network. ○ An RDA multi-site structure with Regions will demonstrate to funders the complementary and mutually beneficial relationship between the RDA and its Regions. Regional websites must remain part of the overarching RDA website to keep sight of the common WG/IG, mission, principles and Plenary details. ● Providing official support and approval for use of the RDA brand in activities and efforts:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ including permission to use the RDA logo and brand in the Formal Arrangement signed with Regions; ○ providing a resource pack with logos and usage guidelines; ○ offering marketing materials (flyers, posters, laptop stickers, slide decks) that can easily be tailored by Regions. ● Resolving and adjudicating conflicts by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ maintaining open and regular dialogue with Regions to avoid conflict between the RDA and Regional interests; ○ providing Regional discussion fora and sharing of activities to pre-empt and reduce conflicts between distinct RDA Regional interests or competing groups within one Region; ○ escalating conflicts to the Council to adjudicate if issues cannot be arbitrated via informal discussions.
Responsibilities	<p>RDA Regions will support the work of the RDA in various ways.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Supporting the vision, mission, and principles of RDA Global at the Regional level by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ hosting Regional workshops and events, using RDA branding; ○ promoting RDA activities at other related data events in the Region; ○ representing national activities in RDA Interest/Working groups; ○ promoting the adoption of outputs by targeted activities profiling potential use cases. ● Fostering a diverse data community by engaging a wide range of stakeholders within the Region to grow RDA impact by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ demonstrating the value of the RDA to individuals in the Region to grow membership; ○ developing Regional mentoring and training programs; ○ engaging and build consensus on nationally important data issues; ○ measuring the impact and adoption of RDA outputs within the Region. ● Supporting regional participation in Plenaries by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ facilitating the hosting of Plenaries with the goal of building the RDA community within the Region and building Regional presence within the RDA (Regions are not required, but encouraged in this role); ○ leveraging RDA Plenaries within their Region to build the data community through side meetings, associated symposia, Regional sponsorships and scholarships, etc. ● Nominating an RDA Individual Member as representative to attend and vote in the Regional Assembly (RA) meetings. <p>Regions will also support the business of the RDA in a variety of ways.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Providing financial contributions as described in the Regional Partnership Processes document¹³. ● Providing in-kind support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ skills, duration and details will be agreed in collaboration with the RDA to ensure the support offered can generate value (See Regional Partnership Processes document for examples); ○ each in-kind staff resource would be provided to the Secretariat at a minimum of 50% of their time; ○ staff may be provided to complete contracted pieces of work (e.g., an analysis of outputs adoption to inform RDA strategy¹⁴). ● Facilitating the hosting and organizing of Plenaries: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ organisation of, and expenses for, Plenaries are the Region's

¹³ 9

¹⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-strategy/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> responsibility. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ host Regions will make a contribution to the RDA in the event of a profit on the Plenary, and as agreed upon prior to the event; ○ hosting governance meetings before, during, or after Plenary. ● Shaping future directions by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ interacting with national research funding bodies, ministries and other government officials to influence data policy and digital agendas; ○ developing robust sustainability plans and business models in collaboration with national funders and governments to ensure continued contribution to the RDA; ○ contributing to RDA business and strategy through multiple means including the Regional Assembly.
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RDA Working Groups

Function	Working Groups (WGs) are engaged in creating Recommendations that will directly enable data sharing, exchange, or interoperability. WGs must produce at least one Recommendation but can also produce other kinds of outputs. WGs operate to a defined objective and on a finite timeline.
Membership	WGs are open to participation from all RDA members. Members are international experts, and ideally the group membership spans at least 3 continents.
Creation	WGs are expected to 1) propose one or more concrete impact-oriented Recommendation(s), 2) include a plan for adoption of the Recommendation(s) within the proposed timeframe and by WG members, and 3) articulate within the Statement of Work what specific community will benefit by adoption of the Recommendation(s) and include representatives of this community within the proposed WG membership. A WG is established once the WG Statement of Work has been endorsed by the Council. Each WG has two or more WG Co-Chairs who serve as the point of contact for the WG.
Duration	The WG is expected to provide a duration and timeline for activity in the Statement of Work. WGs are expected to have a duration of 18 months.
Termination	WGs are normally disbanded upon completion of the Recommendation(s) described within their endorsed Statement of Work or at the end of the timeframe designated within their Statement of Work. Other possible outcomes as described in Creating or Joining an RDA Working Group ² and Closing RDA Groups ¹⁵ are decided on a case by case basis.
Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● WGs have access to appropriate administrative and communications support from the RDA Secretariat. ● WGs' efforts are supported by technical expertise and guidance of the TAB. ● WG Recommendations and other outputs are widely promoted and distributed by the RDA, the Council, the RA and the OA.

¹⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/closing-rda-groups/>

Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WGs are responsible for carrying out the work described in their endorsed Statement of Work without any major variance in scope or stated outputs. • WGs are responsible for the initial adoption of their Recommendation(s) within a community of impact during the duration of WG effort. • WGs are responsible for presenting their work at Plenary meetings and working with the RDA on promotion and outreach about their Recommendation(s) and other outputs. • WGs are encouraged to conduct open discussions on the RDA online platform during the course of their work. • WGs are expected to achieve progress via consensus.
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RDA Interest Groups

Function	Interest Groups (IGs) ³ form to investigate and discuss any issues relevant to the RDA. IGs are composed of experts from the community that are committed to directly or indirectly enabling data sharing, exchange, or interoperability. IGs serve as a platform for communication and coordination among individuals, outside and within the RDA, with shared interests. IGs cannot produce Recommendations but can produce other kinds of outputs. They produce deliverables such as surveys, reports and WG Statement of Work.
Membership	IGs are open to participation from all RDA members. Members should be international experts, and ideally the group should span at least 3 continents.
Creation	An IG is established once the IG Statement of Work (SoW) has been endorsed by the Council. Each IG has two or more IG Chairs who serve as the point of contact for the IG.
Duration	There is no fixed duration for an IG.
Termination	IGs are disbanded on request or when, in the opinion of the Secretariat and after seeking advice from the TAB, they are deemed to be inactive.
Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IGs have access to appropriate administrative and communications support from the RDA Secretariat. • IGs' efforts are supported by technical expertise and guidance from the TAB.
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IGs are responsible for progressing the activities described in their Charter. • IGs are expected to participate in Plenaries on a regular basis. • IGs are encouraged to conduct open discussions on the RDA online platform during the course of their work. • IGs are expected to achieve progress via consensus.

RDA Communities of Practice

Function	Communities of Practice (CoPs) ⁴ form to represent discipline or domain specific communities within RDA as well as to investigate, discuss and provide knowledge and skills on any specific discipline and/or domain issues relevant to the community and RDA. Members of a CoP are experts from the community that are committed to directly or indirectly enabling data sharing, exchange, and/or interoperability. CoPs serve as forums for communication and coordination among individuals with shared interests
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	outside and within RDA. Each CoP will represent RDA activities and achievements in their community and foster bidirectional communication and coordination between the CoP and its community through a series of initiatives, such as ambassador programmes, dedicated events, content, etc.
Membership	CoPs are open to participation from all RDA members with an interest in the CoP's domain / discipline. CoPs should have representatives from at least 10 countries across at least 3 continents. CoPs are encouraged to make sure the Global South is represented in their membership. Each CoP must have three or more Co-Chairs representing at least 3 continents who serve as the point of contact for the CoP.
Creation	The justification for creating a CoP should include a demonstration of substantial level of support for it. It should be global and have the backing of a significant number of individuals and organisations. It should be spearheaded by one or more productive RDA Working or Interest Groups which should have already produced one or more endorsed RDA Recommendation and / or Supporting Outputs. A CoP is established once its CoP Statement of Work has undergone community review, TAB review and OAB and RAB commentary and subsequent endorsement by Council.
Legitimacy	In order to ensure the proposed CoP is truly representative of the community and demonstrates institutional commitment, a CoP has to provide letters of support from major stakeholder organisations in the CoP's discipline / research domain. The RDA community at large has an opportunity to comment and provide feedback on the proposed CoP during the six-week community review period.
Duration	There is no fixed duration for a CoP. Each CoP will undergo a review on an 18 month basis.
Termination	CoPs are disbanded ² in one of the following cases: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On request from a majority of the co-chairs, and with evidence that two-thirds majority of the responding members agree. • If Council considers the CoP to be violating its CoP agreement, the RDA Code of conduct or the RDA Guiding Principles. • If the periodic review executed by RDA Council indicates the CoP should not continue. • If the CoP is considered inactive.
Rights	CoPs have access to appropriate administrative and communications support from the RDA Secretariat. CoPs are provided with a dedicated area on the RDA website, to which they will be offered access and editing rights, in conjunction with the RDA Secretariat. CoPs' efforts are supported by technical expertise and guidance from the TAB and are encouraged to work with the Regional Assembly Board (RAB) and Organisational Assembly Board (OAB).
Responsibilities	CoPs are responsible for progressing the activities described in their CoP Agreement and for upholding the RDA Guiding Principles and Code of Conduct, including achievement of progress via consensus. CoPs are expected to participate in Plenaries on a regular basis, at least in every other Plenary. CoPs are mandated to conduct open discussions on the RDA online platform during the course of their work, and to disseminate information

	<p>via webinars, reports, or other means.</p> <p>CoPs can initiate new IGs and WG which follow the usual RDA processes, including for endorsement. The concept being that the CoP coordinates the discussions and when a specific topic discussion (IG) or solution (WG) is required, the co-chairs coordinate the people to create the Statement of Work (SoW) and start the group process.</p> <p>CoPs must adhere to the RDA Outputs IP, licensing and branding policies. CoPs leverage the RDA WG mechanism to deliver Recommendations and can produce additional Supporting Outputs, just like an Interest Group.</p> <p>CoPs demonstrate and document adoption of RDA Recommendations and Outputs.</p>
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RDA Secretariat

Function	<p>The Secretariat is a distributed team responsible for all matters related to the operations of the RDA. This includes support to the RDA Council and the Regional, Technical and Organisational Advisory Boards, as well as support to the planning and organising of the biannual plenary meetings of the RDA. The Secretariat is responsible for operationalising and implementing the RDA strategy^{Error! Bookmark not defined.}. The Secretariat is funded through the RDA global budget and in-kind staff support.</p>
Staffing	<p>The Secretariat is led by a Secretary General (SG)¹⁶, who is appointed and reviewed by the Council. The SG is responsible for the effective and efficient operation of the distributed Secretariat. All members of the Secretariat work under the direction of the SG. The SG reports to the Council. Poor performance by the SG may result in dismissal by the Council.</p> <p>All members of the Secretariat work under the direction of the Secretary General though members of the Secretariat are employed by many organisations, provided as an in-kind contribution by RDA organisational members. RDA staff provided by organisational members are hosted within their home organizations but for RDA purposes report to the RDA Secretary General. The size and constitution of Secretariat staff is described in the annual Operating Plan and approved by Council.</p>
Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The SG participates as a non-voting consensus-forming member of the RDA Council.
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Secretariat will support the activities of the IGs, WGs, Plenary, the Council, the OA, RA and TAB as appropriate including logistical, administrative, and other support. • The Secretariat is responsible for operating the RDA in line with the RDA strategy. <p>The Secretariat is responsible for events and other planning for the RDA bi-annual Plenaries.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Secretariat is responsible for communications and promotion of RDA efforts and outputs, including the development of appropriate reports to stakeholder groups and partners. • The Secretariat is responsible for open dissemination of RDA strategic documents. • The Secretariat is expected to work with the Council Nominations Committee, the OA, RA and TAB to conduct elections for the Council, OAB, RAB and TAB members respectively.

¹⁶ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/secretary-general/>

RDA Secretary General Roles and Responsibilities

Membership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Engage with and represent the RDA membership in accordance with the guiding principles of the RDA. ● Communicate with all members regarding the progress and issues facing the RDA. ● Apply international experience in dealing with members and supporters from many countries with different cultures. ● Assist RDA Working and Interest Groups. ● Liaise with Organisational and Affiliate Member Organisations
Organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Deal with main issues facing the RDA as the field develops and be alert to changes in technology, practice, and international legal changes that affect access, intellectual property rights, and other related issues. ● Participate, together with RDA Council, in strategic planning that transitions RDA from being a start-up to a mature, sustainable organisation. ● Drive and manage change in line with strategic plans ● Advocate with current and future funders and other stakeholders. ● Develop and grow an organisational culture reflective of the RDA Guiding Principles.
Outreach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Present the work of the RDA to audiences from a wide variety of backgrounds, including future supporters. ● Represent the RDA in discussions with other parties and associated organisations, be political and sensitive to cultural differences of supporters. ● Travel widely on behalf of the RDA, especially to potential new countries that may wish to join the RDA in some capacity.
Council	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Attend all meetings of Council and appropriate Regional, Technical and Organisational Advisory Board meetings and liaise with their chairs on a regular basis. ● Report to Council on Finance. ● Work with Council and the Financial Subcommittee to develop and maintain the RDA Foundation's budget.
Administration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Manage the RDA Secretariat. ● Participate actively in the work of the Secretariat. ● Operate the RDA Foundation (RDA legal entity) ● Be responsible for the finances and other issues of governance of the RDA Foundation as a legal entity. The Secretary General is the responsible accounting officer for the purposes of tax and conforming to the legal requirements of a not for profit company under UK law. ● Be familiar with UK Charity and Company law in as much as it affects the legal entity. ● Prepare annual accounts and report for submission to the UK Charity Commission.

RDA Technical Advisory Board

Function	The Technical Advisory Board (TAB) provides technical expertise and advice to the Council, and helps to develop and review RDA CoPs, WGs and IGs to promote their impact and effectiveness.
Membership	<p>Members of the TAB are elected from and by the RDA membership. Each year, approximately one-third of the TAB stand down and their positions are filled by election. The TAB members normally serve for a term of 3 years and may be re-elected for one additional term. Details of the processes governing TAB membership are described in the TAB Responsibilities and Processes document¹⁷.</p> <p>The TAB chooses TAB members to act as Co-Chairs for a term of two years. There should be at least one co-chair for every five members of TAB to coordinate the work of the TAB.</p>
Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The TAB is supported by the Secretariat in executing its activities. • At least one of the Co-Chairs of the TAB participates as a non-voting consensus-forming observer member of the RDA Council. • At least one of the Co-Chairs of the TAB participates as a non-voting consensus-forming observer member of the OAB and RAB.
Responsibilities	<p>The TAB has three streams of activity: technical, strategic, and organisational. In each of these, the TAB members should not promote special interests, domains, regions or disciplines.</p> <p>From a strategic perspective, the TAB:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides advice to the Council to inform strategic approaches and decisions; • Advises the RDA membership and the Council on impact-oriented RDA groups' opportunities and discussion topics. <p>From a technical perspective, the TAB:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultivates candidate group Statements of Work (SoW), and RDA Outputs that promote the RDA goals of adoption and impact; • Assesses candidate group Statements of Work (SoW)s and provides feedback to ensure they are achievable and meet the RDA goals; • Assigns a TAB member as liaison for each CoP, WG and IG; • Works with RDA CoPs, WGs and IGs, the RAB and the OAB to promote adoption and effectiveness of their Outputs; • Works with the Council, if requested, to evaluate CoP, IG and WG Outputs; • Works with the OAB, if requested, to help them evaluate CoP, WG and IG Outputs; • Where necessary, reviews and approves session proposals ahead of Plenaries and provides guidance to CoP, WG and IG Chairs for their proposal submissions; • Works with CoP, WG and IG chairs ahead of Plenaries to solicit attendance. <p>From an organisational perspective, the TAB:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reviews the group meeting schedule for Plenaries to minimise clashes. • Coordinates with the OAB on the adoptability of outputs.

¹⁷ Research Data Alliance. (2020). RDA TAB Responsibilities and Processes (2.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/E9F94145-5EA1-44CC-9428-85498CF85E30>

RDA Organisational Advisory Board

Function	The Organisational Advisory Board (OAB) is constituted from representatives of RDA Organisational Members and Affiliates and provides advice to the Council on RDA organisational and process issues, overarching strategy, etc.
Membership	Organisational Members nominate an Individual Member of the RDA as representative of the organisation to be a member of the Organisational Assembly (OA), which in turn elects the OAB. The election process is described in the RDA Organisational Membership Processes document. Member organisations may also designate alternate representatives. Only one representative from each organisation can vote at any particular OA meeting. Member organisations may replace their organisational representatives or alternate representatives at their discretion.
Co-chair(s)	The OAB chooses one Co-Chair annually for a term of two years. The two Co-Chairs coordinate the work of the OAB. OAB Co-chairs are elected by the OAB members, through a simple majority voting with one vote for each OAB member. OAB Co-chairs are elected for 2 years at a time with a maximum of one consecutive re-election (i.e. maximum 4 years). The Co-chair elections are staggered so that one Co-chair is elected each year. After their time as Co-chair, regardless of whether they were elected a Co-chair for one or two consecutive two-year periods, an OAB member is ineligible to be re-elected as an OAB Co-chair until 2 years have passed.
Duration	Representatives of Organisational Members may serve on the OAB as long as their organisations are approved Organisational Members of the RDA. The Council approves and removes Organisational Affiliates and delegates the decision on Organisational Member expiration (e.g. non-payment of annual fee) and revocation (e.g. non-compliance with the RDA guiding principles) to the OAB. Where necessary the Council will make the final decision.
Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The OAB is supported by the Secretariat in executing its activities. • At least one of the Co-Chairs of the OAB participates as a non-voting consensus-forming observer member of the RDA Council.
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The OAB provides input to the Council on any aspect of RDA's work, with a particular remit to consider the organisational processes, structure, strategic direction, and sustainability of the RDA and the adoptability of RDA outputs. • OAB members are expected to subscribe to the RDA Guiding Principles and attend the OAB meetings and the bi-annual Plenaries. • OAB members are expected to act as conduits between their organisations and the RDA.

Regional Advisory Board

Function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oversee the activities of the RAB/RA • Provide advice to the Council on issues of interest to the Regions. • Inform and steer the Council on regional issues. • Bring issues and concerns from RDA Regions to the Council, and from the Council to the Regions. • Seek consensus and resolve any differences of opinion across Regions.
Membership	RAB members are RA members representing contributing Regions that have been elected to the RAB. The RAB consists of up to 12 elected members including 2 Co-Chairs, and some additional participants as described below.

	RAB members are elected for two years. Each year, the terms of half of the elected RAB members expire. Until there is a full RAB with 12 members, there are no restrictions on re-election. Once there is a full RAB, there will be a limit of at most one consecutive re-election, and a person can only be on RAB for a maximum of 4 out of 6 consecutive years.
	<p>The RAB chooses one Co-Chair annually for a term of two years. The two Co-Chairs coordinate the work of the RAB.</p> <p>RAB Co-Chairs are elected by the RAB members, through a simple majority voting with one vote for each RAB member. RAB Co-Chairs are elected for 2 years at a time with a maximum of one consecutive re-election (i.e., maximum of 4 years). The Co-Chair elections are staggered so that one Co-Chair is elected each year. After their time as Co-Chair, regardless of whether they were elected a Co-Chair for one or two consecutive two-year periods, an RAB member is ineligible to be re-elected as an RAB Co-Chair until 2 years have passed.</p> <p>The RAB Co-Chair elections are held immediately after the RAB elections with voting by the new RAB members.</p> <p>If there is more than one candidate, each RAB Co-Chair is elected by simple majority voting with one vote for each RAB member.</p> <p>There is an exception for the first year of the RAB. The RAB members will agree on a process to ensure staggered terms for the RAB Co-Chairs.</p>
Duration	Representatives of RDA Regions may serve on the RAB as long as their regions are partner RDA Regions. The Council decides on Regional Member expiration (e.g., non-payment of contributions) and revocation (e.g., non-compliance with the RDA guiding principles and Code of Conduct) to the RAB.
Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Directly provides input to the Council and the Secretary General. • At least one Co-chair of the RAB participates as a non-voting consensus-forming member of the RDA Council. • The RAB is supported by the RDA Secretariat in executing its activities.
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the smooth running of the RA & RAB. • Chair and manage the RA meetings • The RAB provides input to the Council on any aspect of RDA's work, with a particular remit to consider regional processes, structure, strategies, issues and concerns. • RAB members are expected to subscribe to the RDA Guiding Principles, Code of Conduct and attend the RAB meetings and RDA Plenaries. • RAB members are expected to act as conduits between their Regions and the RDA. • Elect RAB Co-Chairs to organize RAB meetings and participate in the Council.

RDA Council

Function	The RDA Council is responsible for the overall oversight, success, strategy, business plan and sustainability of the RDA. The Council is the decision-making body of the RDA, acting and deciding on input from the RDA membership and other bodies. Decisions in the Council are made via consensus, and when consensus cannot be reached, any voting Council member can call for a vote.
Membership	The Council is an elected body of the RDA. Its voting members are "statespersons" committed to enabling broad and robust international scientific and research data infrastructures, and not to promoting special interests, regions, domains or disciplines. Council is a senior body of statespersons not explicitly representing any constituency. They need to be mindful of the needs of funders, the membership, partners, and all relevant stakeholders, but also willing to make difficult strategic decisions that may not please all.

	<p>There are five kinds of non-voting consensus-forming members of the RDA Council: Co-chairs of the TAB, Co-Chairsof the OAB, Co-Chairs of the RAB, legal entity host organization representative and the Secretary General. The Council terms are structured so that 3 voting members of the Council are elected each year.</p>
Election	<p>Candidate Council members are nominated by a Nominations Committee, a committee of the Council that is responsible for nominating Council members. The Nominations Committee is appointed by the current RDA Council. Details of the membership of the Nominations Committee (including the conditions for admission to and termination of such membership) and the regulations governing Nominations Committee proceedings are set out in the the Nominations Committee Terms of Reference¹⁸.</p> <p>The Nominations Committee calls for nominations through the RDA Secretariat. The Nominations Committee provides a set of eligible candidates, considering individual capability, the purpose of the Council, and the balance of Council membership. This set is presented to the RDA Membership and the community is invited to vote according to the RDA election procedures (adapted from the RDA Technical Advisory Board election process). All RDA members are eligible to vote in the elections and an on-line voting system is used to conduct the election. Each year, the Council normally selects one Co-Chair to serve a two-year term, at the first face to face meeting after the close of the election period. Each Co-Chair should have an overlapping term with the other Co-Chair. The two Co-Chairs coordinate the work of the Council. A council member may serve for a maximum of two consecutive two-year terms.</p> <p>Upon termination of their term on the Council, a Co-Chair may continue to engage for a limited time, with the approval of Council members, to extend their term to ensure a smooth, efficient and timely handover to the new Co-Chair.</p>
Term	<p>Council member term is for three years and members may re-nominate themselves for one successive term. Council members whose terms end officially step down when the next set of Council member candidates is accepted. If the candidates are not elected, then the existing Council members remain in office until new Council members are elected.</p> <p>When a Council Member’s term is completed they will hand over their responsibilities in an orderly fashion to their successor.</p>
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Council is responsible for setting RDA's strategic direction and disseminating it by maintaining and evolving the RDA Strategic Plan. ● Council is responsible for the ultimate vote on governance and organisational matters. ● Council is responsible for the long-term financial sustainability of the Research Data Alliance (see item on Trustees below). ● Council members are expected to actively participate in all Council and Plenary meetings. In the event of non-attendance for the duration of one year, their term will be viewed as effectively completed and they will be invited to resign from Council. ● Council members are expected to contribute to and represent the RDA in a manner that facilitates the successful accomplishment of its goals, mission and vision. ● Council is responsible for reviewing and evaluating the RDA Operations Plan, including the annual plan of activities and budget which sets the organisational membership framework. ● Council approves and removes Organisational Affiliates and delegates the

¹⁸ RDA Council Nominations Committee Terms of Reference (0.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00082>

	<p>decision on OM expiration (e.g. non-payment of annual fee) and revocation (e.g. non-compliance with the RDA guiding principles and Code of Conduct) to the OAB. Where necessary, Council will make the final decision.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Council is responsible for reviewing and evaluating all candidate CoP, WG and IG Statements of Work (SoW) for impact and alignment with the goals of the RDA. • Council endorses WG Recommendations upon demonstration of community consensus and successful adoption. <p>Council members are the Trustees of the RDA Foundation and have the financial and legal responsibilities described in the Articles of Association¹⁹.</p>
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RDA Council Executive Committee Session

The RDA Council Executive Committee Session, which is composed of the voting Members of the RDA Council as well as the RDA Legal Entity Host Organisation Representative, meets at the beginning of each face-to-face Council meeting and other times as needed. It is chaired by one of the Council Co-Chairs and considers issues which typically require a confidential discussion or vote of voting Members, such as the RDA Foundation or Secretariat HR issues, as part of the Trustees role. Items discussed at these Executive Committee Sessions will be listed in the Council minutes that follow the Executive Committee Session.

RDA Legal Entity Host Organisation Representative

The RDA Foundation (RDA legal entity)²⁰ is a non-profit charitable organisation registered with Companies House England and Wales since April 2014 (Company No: 09021881) and with the Charities Commission since July 2015 (Registered Charity Number: 1162762). The RDA legal entity headquarters are hosted by UKRI STFC (Host organisation). The Host Organisation, as outlined in the Memorandum of Understanding, nominates a representative of STFC to be a non-voting consensus forming member of the RDA Council. The main role and responsibility of this representative is to liaise between the Foundation’s hosting organisation and RDA Council to ensure good ethical, financial, legal and organisational conduct of the RDA Foundation in UK. Furthermore, this representative is a member of the RDA Financial Subcommittee (FSC) to provide access and insights to the financial aspects of the legal entity.

RDA Council Subcommittees

The RDA Council Subcommittees are focused groups responsible for aspects of the RDA Council’s work. They consider specific topics and provide recommendations and options for the RDA Council to decide. The membership of these Council Subcommittees is mostly drawn from the membership of the RDA Council, TAB, RAB and OAB Representatives, and legal entity host organization representative at Council, as well as the RDA Secretary General. Other RDA members can also be invited to join.

In addition to the standing Finance, Legal and Nominations Subcommittees, other subcommittees may be created on a standing or ad hoc basis as required. Subcommittees are dissolved when their work is complete. Ultimate responsibility and authority for the work of the subcommittees lies with Council itself. Subcommittees are expected to report to Council on a regular basis, with the mechanism and frequency to be determined by Council for each subgroup.

RDA Council Finance Subcommittee

¹⁹ <https://zenodo.org/record/1404105/files/AOA.pdf>

²⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-foundation/>

Function	The Finance Subcommittee is responsible for the oversight and due vigilance of the finances of the RDA. The Subcommittee is also responsible for the financial audit of the RDA Foundation. The Subcommittee monitors and reports on the RDA finances at every RDA Council meeting and brings to the attention of the Council all issues arising. Support is provided by the RDA Secretariat, and expert audit advice is secured as required.
Membership	Membership comprises at least three Council members, preferably from different regions, the Secretary General, the Financial Officer of the Secretariat, the legal entity host organisation representative and an OAB member. Membership is agreed by the RDA Council.
Duration	Membership is for the duration of the member's term of election (for members of Council or the OAB) or as invited by Council for other members. Upon completion of their terms, members hand over their responsibilities in an orderly fashion to their successors. Finance Subcommittee members are expected to contribute actively to the work of the Subcommittee, and in the event of non-contribution for longer than one year, the member is invited to resign from the Subcommittee.
Rights	The Finance Subcommittee is supported by the RDA Secretariat, and expert audit advice will be secured as required.
Responsibilities	The Council Finance Subcommittee is responsible for the financial oversight of the centralized funds of the RDA and all funds in the RDA Foundation. Funding for individual RDA regions is not the responsibility of the Subcommittee. The Subcommittee is responsible for reporting on all aspects of the finances to the RDA Council, and bringing to the attention of Council any and all issues arising. The Subcommittee is responsible for the audit of the RDA Foundation.

RDA Council Legal Subcommittee

Function	The Legal Subcommittee is an ad hoc Committee convened by the Council when needed to discuss and make recommendations to the Council on specific legal affairs of the RDA.
Membership	Membership comprises legal experts from the RDA membership in addition to at least three Council members, preferably from different regions. Membership is agreed by the RDA Council.
Duration	Membership is for the duration of the discussion for which the Committee was convened.
Rights	The Legal Subcommittee is supported by the RDA Secretariat, and expert legal advice is secured as required.
Responsibilities	The Council Legal Subcommittee is responsible for making recommendations as directed by Council. Individual regional legal issues are not the responsibility of the Sub Committee. Legal issues may include (and are not limited to) IPR and brand of the RDA, Data Protection for the RDA, indemnification and contracts.

RDA Council Nominations Committee

Function	<p>Candidate Council members are nominated by a Nominations Committee, a subcommittee of the Council that is responsible for nominating Council members.</p> <p>The Nominations Committee calls for nominations through the RDA Secretariat. The Nominations Committee then provides a set of candidates, taking into account individual capability, the purpose of Council, and the balance of Council membership. This set is presented to the RDA Membership and the community is invited to vote according to the RDA election procedures (adapted from the RDA Technical Advisory Board election process). All RDA members are eligible to vote in the elections and an on-line voting system is used to conduct the election.</p>
Membership	<p>The Nominations Committee is appointed by the current RDA Council. Details of the membership of the Nominations Committee (including the conditions for admission to and termination of such membership) and the regulations governing Nominations Committee proceedings are set out in the Nominations Committee Terms of Reference¹⁸.</p>
Duration	<p>Membership is for a one year term.</p>
Rights	<p>The Nomination Committee is supported by the RDA Secretariat.</p>
Responsibilities	<p>The RDA Nominations Committee is responsible for creating a list of eligible candidate Council members that the RDA membership votes on.</p>